

The “R” Approach for Modeling a Reconfiguration Problem in Smart Grid Networks

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Abstract

Ensure higher levels of continuity and reliability for the electricity supply service are some of the requirements of consumers and electric power providers in the Smart Grid (SG) context. Reconfiguration of distribution networks aims to support the decision support, planning and/or real-time control of the operation of the electricity network. The goal of this paper is to propose a modelling approach for the reconfiguration problem based on R in order to better support the decision making process. Beyond that, R modelling of electricity networks may additionally support scalability evaluation, allows flexible re-configuration analysis and potentially improves the response time when handling issues of network reconfiguration using graph theory.

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1 Introduction

Electricity has become an essential consumer goods to society. In this way, a fault or short circuit at a point on the network, the absence, or even small disruptions in supply, which are characterized by reduced terminal voltage of consumption and near zero levels circuits, can cause several disorders both in economic sphere and the social sphere. The continuity of electricity supply is evaluated through indicators that measure the frequency and duration of interruptions occurring on consumers [1].

A fault or short circuit at a certain point in the network makes a protective device operates, leaving whole load (consumers) connected from that point without electricity supply. The need

to initiate a process of reconfiguring a network of electricity has at least three capital motives [2]: (i) performing maintenance on the components of the electric grid; (ii) an imbalance of electric power; and (iii) power failure.

In general, the problem of reconfiguration of power networks aims to seek an optimal operation strategy with the intention of minimize losses and provide an appropriate balancing of the loads in the system, taking into account the protection and quality of electricity supply to consumers.

The modelling of a reconfiguration problem based on “R” in the Smart Grid context presented in this paper aims to propose a flexible modeling for protection solutions, optimization, and dynamic generation. The proposed modelling approach deals with disorders of a power system in regard to interruption of supply of electric power and other anomalies.

2 Related Work

The reconfiguration of power system is difficult to deal due to its combinatorial nature [3]. The difficulty in mathematical formulation to fulfill the constraints (of the problem) used to model the behavior of system elements, with appropriate computational time for decision making in real-time, are not taken into account the most recent research [4][5][6] in relation to a solution of reconfiguration in real-time.

The problem consists in finding, among all possible combinations, a set of configurations which (i) minimize the number of switching operations while keeping the radial structure of the system (no formation of rings), (ii) reduce the energy loss and (iii) reducing the amount of consumers without electricity supply, in order to safeguarding restrictions voltage levels at the point of load, maximum current flow in the branches, the lines flow capacity and nominal power of the transformers.

The graph theory together with the laws of the mesh nodes Kirchoff and the theory of circuits, have been used to support the representation of diverse applications, simulations and analysis of power networks. An abstract model, in graph form, of a power network was proposed by [7], which a node (vertex) representing a bus and an edge represents a transmission line connecting two buses.

In [8], a graph theory is used, particularly a directed graph to represent a power networks in order to determine the contributions of specific generators in terms of power flows at different loads. Each vertex is considered a root generator and the edges represent transmission lines, from which it generates all possible subgraphs oriented.

Another use of graph theory is found in [9], in which the problem to estimate the location of faulty components (Fault Section Estimation - FSC) is transformed into a problem of partitioning the vertices of graphs leading into account the priorities of these to spawn new subsets of graphs connected and balanced.

A methodology of protection directed to an intentional islanding of service-oriented power systems of partitioning its graph based on network topology and power flow through its buses was proposed by [10].

A proposal to improve the reliability of radial distribution system with distributed generation after the occurrence of a failure in the external power grid was presented by [11]. Algorithms based on graphs are used to maximize the amount of load to be supported in case of isolation and for planning the location of circuit breakers in a network of power distribution. The idea is to define new circuit breakers and handle the existing ones to define the area of operation of distributed generation.

A method for islanding detection area in large power systems through sectioning of edges or minimal set of cut was proposed by [12]. The method can determine the location where islanding occurred after the incidence of electrical malfunctions using search algorithms for width and depth of graph theory.

The graph theory was used by [13] to represent the entire electrical system based on the configuration states of circuit breakers that connect the components of the power network. It was proposed a method for reconfiguration and restoration of electricity supply in contingency situations using genetic algorithms. In the genetic algorithm, we use the representation of a chromosome to represent the configuration of a set of circuit breakers belonging to the electrical system.

3 Problems and Motivations

The modelling of a reconfiguration problem based on R in the Smart Grid context aims to deal and assist in the decision making in regard to performance towards reconfiguration problems of the power grid. Possible reconfiguration scenarios are listed below:

- Situation 1: Interruption the service supply of electric power to end users.
 - *Strategy*: Identify and isolate (protect) the power network, safeguarding the integrity of the network;
 - *Action*: Reconfigure the power network in a autonomic way with the intention of restore the power supply using a SG (Smart Grid) algorithm based on graph teory, taking into account the selection of the “optimal” solution applicable in a matrix combinatorial topological distribution (route versus electrical boundaries of the electrical grid).
- Situation 2: Optimization in supply of electric power: network reconfiguration and load balancing.
 - *Strategy*: Identify points of attention (warnings of possible overloads - threatened thresholds);
 - *Action*: Propose improvement in the quality of service of electricity supply proposing a more optimized configuration of alternative network, while respecting the constraints of voltage levels, ability to flow lines and nominal power of the transformers.
- Situation 3: Distributed Generation (DG) - Network reconfiguration and load balancing.
 - *Strategy*: Check the demand and / or load variation and identify the distributed energy sources connected to the power network as well as their respective loads available;
 - *Action*: Propose an optimum and balanced topology network with the inclusion of distributed generation sources.

4 Modelling with “R”

Computer modeling helps in proposing solutions to scientific problems using simulation. To this end, we analyze the phenomena, develop mathematical models for describing the problem, and prepare computer codes to support the solutions.

The computational model presented aims to propose a “R” based modeling of protection solutions, optimization, and dynamic generation that deals disorders of a power system in regard to interruption of supply of electric power and other anomalies.

The system has a configuration that includes a set of circuits that are energized, forming a tree from the point of view of graph theory. The circuits that are not energized are called branches of connection (disconnected graph), and a suitable replacement (a connection from a reconfiguration) of a branch connection with a branch of the tree creates a new tree (a power system reconfigured) represented by a new connected graph (in which there is always a path consisting of branches between any two nodes).

Given a connect graph $G = (V, E)$ and $(degree(v_i) \geq 1)$ without loops ($e_i = (v_i, v_i) \notin G$) which V corresponds to the set of vertices, $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$, and E corresponds to the set of edges, $E = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}$, this may represent an infrastructure reconfiguration of power networks, as shown in Figure 1, as follows:

Figure 1: Mapping computational model of the power grid

- The set of vertices V represents the generator supplying (AL) and the intersections of the transmission lines.
- The set of edges E represents the transmission lines. Each edges e_i may contain a set of devices (such as circuit breakers and distributed generators) beyond the transmission line properties. The representation of these data is accomplished through a three-dimensional matrix $M = (d \times p \times e)$ (Figure 01), in which:
 - The line (d) represents the devices;
 - The column (p) stores the properties of the devices and the segment of the transmission line between the device and its predecessor.
 - Dimension (e) of the matrix (M) stores the devices (d) and its properties (p).

5 Simulation Scenario

In this section, we present an application of network reconfiguration focused on infrastructure analysis. In [8], a method using graph theory for determining the contribution of each generator to each load in the system has been presented. The method is mathematically performed

without assistance of computational tools which may cause delays in the computation depending on the size of the environment to be analyzed.

In this paper, the validation of the flexible modeling will be presented (which uses graph theory), simple and algorithmic by mapping the results of [8], using algorithms developed in simulation environment named “R” [14] and Igraph package.

“R” is a language and environment for statistical computing that provides a wide variety of statistical (linear and nonlinear modeling, classical statistical tests, time series analysis, classification, clustering, among others) and graphical techniques, and is highly extensible.

Igraph is a free software package for creating and manipulating undirected and directed graphs. It includes implementations for classic graph theory problems like minimum spanning trees and network flow, and also implements algorithms for some recent methods for analyzing network such as the pursuit of community structure.

Figure 2: Why one should use EasyChair

In [8], a IEEE standard 6-bus (Figure 2) test system is used. This system have generators (A, B, C, D), buses (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6), transmission lines and their respective loads.

Figure 3: Oriented graph modelling a IEEE 6-bus system

Then the mapping of graph theory is presented. Based on the direction of the flows in all the branches of the 6-bus system, a oriented graph is constructed. Such mapping was redesigned according to new modeling seen in Figure 3 with orange dot represents generation buses (1,3,6),

light-blue dot represents load buses and gray dot could represent the load of a neighborhood, a city or even a microgrid.

A subgraph of a graph G is a graph whose vertex set is a subset of that of G , and whose adjacency relation is a subset of that of G restricted to this subset. In this mapping, subgraphs are constructed in such a way that the power can reach to all vertices in that subgraphs. Figure 4 shows a subgraph of generator C.

Figure 4: Root subgraph of Generator C

After the development of the algorithms according to the mathematical calculations based on article [8] using “R” approach, we obtained the same results as shown in Table 1.

	Load 2	Load 4	Load 5
Generator A	0.3333	0.0000	0.0000
Generator B	0.2500	0.7500	0.5000
Generator C	0.4167	0.2500	0.5000

Table 1: Contribution of each generator to each load in the system

The Table 1 shows the individuals contributions of each generator to the loads. AS we can, the Load 4 receives 75% power from Generator B and 25% from Generator C, but its load don’t receives any contribution of generator A.

The model is flexible and with this information (Table 1) allows to propose a network reconfiguration to make the system optimized, thus minimizing dependence on a single transformer, thereby reducing the consequences of a possible failure.

6 Final Considerations

The modelling of a reconfiguration problem based on “R” in the Smart Grid context has been discussed and illustrated. The proposed modelling approach used a graph theory and deals with disorders of a power system in regard to interruption of supply of electric power and other anomalies.

The model is adaptable to the context of network reconfiguration and can expand beyond the situations presented. For future work, adapting the model to simulate random loads transformer proposing (i) an autonomic decision making to the system before a failed transformer or a insertion of distributed energy resources; (ii) propose, in real time, a network reconfiguration aiming to balance the loads (optimization) and the minimization of possible occurrences of failures due to overload.

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